

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D4.2 Technical description of E-HYPE and LISFLOOD

Report

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1. Executive Summary

This FOCCUS deliverable **D4.2** summarizes the current state of the existing European hydrological and riverine transport modelling efforts by Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) and the European Commission Joint Research Center (JRC). WP4 in FOCCUS aims to improve the existing models and to advance high quality freshwater inputs to better support coastal modelling efforts. The 2024 preliminary models outputs are issued as a deliverable **D4.1** and shared within the entire Project Consortium.

The SMHI's model, E-HYPE4, and the JRC modelling system, LISFLOOD and GREEN, have many similarities, e.g. in input data sources, and many differences, especially when it comes to model structure and resolution. This deliverable describes the models with respect to four different aspects: model structure, data, calibration strategy, and results and limitations.

Model structure focuses on spatial and temporal resolution but also on calculation routines describing how the model simulates rainfall-runoff processes and fate and transport processes for nutrients. E-HYPE4 is a semi-distributed model with catchments of a median size 170 km² while LISFLOOD is a distributed model with a grid of 1 arcmin. GREEN is also a catchment-based model with a catchment size 7km², producing nutrient loads at an annual scale. E-HYPE4 calculates both discharge and nutrients at a daily scale.

The data section describes which data were used for the model setup, calibration, and validation. There is a significant overlap in the data used for both models as both systems take advantage of the available open-source datasets for Europe or globally.

Calibration strategies are quite different. E-HYPE4 presented here uses the same parameters for the same hydrological unit regardless of its location. Nutrient modules underwent only a preliminary calibration, intended as the first test of nutrients setup. GREEN has seven regions calibrated separately to improve local model performance.

E-HYPE4 and JRC models can be used in different applications. If daily nutrients are of importance E-HYPE4 would be recommended. The JRC model has a long time series of annual outputs that can be used for marine models under historic conditions and for policy scenarios. Moreover, using both models in an ensemble is recommended to better assess uncertainties inherent with individual models.. Both modelling systems will be further improved in FOCCUS and thorough comparison of models will be conducted in future deliverables.

2. Background

Two different continental hydrological and nutrient models have been developed independently by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) and by the Joint Research Center (JRC). The models produce time series of stream discharge as well as nutrient loads and concentrations. These time series serve as a benchmark for estimating freshwater inflows to European coasts.

The Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE, Lindström et al., 2010) model is an open-source, physically-based, semi-distributed model developed by SMHI to simulate water quantity and quality (SMHI, 2023). LISFLOOD is a spatially distributed water resources model developed by the JRC (since 1997). The GREEN model (Geospatial Regression Equation for European Nutrient losses, Grizzetti et al. 2008; 2012) is a conceptual statistical model used to assess annual nitrogen and phosphorus loads from land to sea, and to represent the effects of management measures to reduce nutrient pollution (Grizzetti et al. 2021, Vigiak et al. 2023; Pistocchi et al. 2023). It is informed by LISFLOOD discharge. Nutrient loads estimated by the HYPE and GREEN models have been used as input to marine models (e.g. Ruvalcaba Baroni et al, 2023; Friedland et al. 2021; Piroddi et al. 2021).

This deliverable describes both models. The following sections describe model structure and calculation routines, data used to develop the European application of the model, calibration strategy, and results and limitations for the current version available at the time of writing this deliverable. Within FOCCUS, both models will be improved to provide more reliable estimates of freshwater inflows to European coasts.

3. SMHI's Freshwater Model, E-HYPE4

3.1. Model structure

HYPE's spatial representation consists of subbasins characterized according to hydrological response units called Soil type – Land Use Combination (SLC) classes. Each HYPE SLC class represents a unique combination of physical properties such as land use, soil type, elevation, soil depth, and/or crop/vegetation cover. HYPE simulations are typically performed using a daily time step, but the model has also been applied with 1-hour and 6-hour time steps. Model outputs are typically aggregated across the subbasin area or are generated for the subbasin outlet point with an option to select outputs on the SLC level.

Routines are included in HYPE for most major land surface and subsurface processes including: snow/ice accumulation and melting, evapotranspiration, surface and macropore flow, soil moisture, discharge generation, groundwater fluctuation, aquifer recharge/discharge, irrigation, abstractions, and routing through rivers, lakes and reservoirs. HYPE's model routines are controlled through general parameters, which provide a single value across the model domain, as well as through parameters that are dependent upon a specific property (typically soil type or land use), which allow for spatial variability in the routine's behavior.

Complete documentation of all available HYPE's model routines can be found in SMHI (2023). Here we highlight the model routines and options relevant to the setup and calibration of E-HYPE4, specifically E-HYPE version 4.2.2. The version of the HYPE model code used throughout this study was version 5.23.0. Detailed description of E-HYPE4 can be found in Brendel et al. (2023).

3.1.1. Hydrological routines

HYPE includes routines to simulate both snow and glacier processes. In E-HYPE4, snowfall and snowmelt processes are simulated using the degree-day method. The fraction of precipitation falling as snow is calculated according to a threshold temperature that can vary with land use. Glacier SLCs consist of two parts: a glacier and a snowfield. Individually, the glacier and snowfield have variable areas, but the total area is always constant. Snow and glacier melting is proportional to temperature when the temperature is greater than a land use dependent threshold temperature, and the potential snow that melts can be tuned with an additional land use dependent parameter.

The local runoff from a subbasin is calculated as the sum of runoff from the land surface (infiltration excess overland flow), runoff from the individual soil layers (interflow), and runoff through subsurface drainage pipes (see Figure 3-1). Overland flow is computed according to runoff coefficients and thresholds for infiltration and soil moisture. In this routine, the total water available for infiltration — the sum of rainfall and snowmelt — is diverted into three flow paths: overland flow to the nearest stream, macropore flow to the soil layer where the groundwater table is currently located, and infiltration to the top soil layer.

Water retention in the soil layers is based on the wilting point, field capacity, and effective porosity. Overland and macropore flows may be generated if the total water available for infiltration exceeds the soil type dependent maximum infiltration rate threshold. In order for macropore flow to be generated, the soil moisture in the topsoil layer must also exceed a soil type dependent soil moisture threshold. Percolation from an upper to lower soil layer occurs when the soil moisture in the upper layer is greater than the layer's field capacity, and the amount of percolation that occurs is limited by model parameters specifying the maximum percolation rates between the soil layers.

Potential evapotranspiration (PET) is simulated in E-HYPE4 using a Modified Jensen-Haise/McGuinness model as a function of temperature, crop cover, extraterrestrial radiation, and latent heat of vaporization. Actual evapotranspiration is equal to PET if the soil moisture exceeds a large proportion (HYPE's I_p parameter) of the soil field capacity but decreases linearly to zero when the soil moisture is below the wilting point. The calculated irrigation water demand for each irrigated land use class for each day of the simulation is withdrawn from defined irrigation sources and applied to the irrigated land use classes while accounting for water losses between demand, withdrawal, and application.

Figure 3-1. Schematic describing runoff calculation routines in HYPE

HYPE uses a conceptual approach to describe the routing of flow between rivers and lakes. HYPE includes two types of rivers: local rivers and main rivers. Local rivers represent the ditches, streams, and rivers within a subbasin that receive only runoff from the subbasin. In contrast, main rivers represent the rivers that receive water from upstream subbasins. The overland flow and runoff from the soil zone for a subbasin are first routed to the local river according to recession parameters depending on soil type and slope. Then, a portion of the flow in the local river can be routed through a local lake representing all of the lakes within a sub basin that receive only runoff from the subbasin (i.e. no contributions from upstream subbasins). The flow exiting the local river and the outflow from the local lake are routed to the main river where it is added to the flow from any upstream subbasins. Translation and dispersion of the main river flow is simulated using a linear channel in series with a linear reservoir (Elenius and Lindström, 2022). Before being passed to downstream subbasins, the main river flow can be routed through an outlet lake/reservoir for which rating curves and regulations can be specified.

3.1.2. Water quality routines

Many water quality constituents can be simulated in HYPE, and these include nitrogen, phosphorus, organic carbon, sediment, silica, general constituent, and water temperature. HYPE simulates nitrogen in soil both as immobile soil pools and as fractions dissolved in soil water. Nitrogen is simulated in two fractions, inorganic nitrogen and organic nitrogen,

Similarly, phosphorus is simulated as soluble (reactive) phosphorus and particulate phosphorus.

Sources of nutrients include discharges from wastewater treatment plants, contributions from septic tanks and other rural sources of wastewater, atmospheric deposition, and application of fertilizers. Fertilizers can be applied up to two times per year for each of the fertilization forms, which are inorganic (commercial) fertilizer and organic fertilizer (e.g. manure). Crop management practices such as date of fertilizer application, fraction of fertilizer that is tilled into the soil, planting, tilling, and harvest dates, crop residual practices, or crop cover fractions are also specified.

Transport and transformations of nutrients then take place in lakes and rivers. For lakes, the whole water volume is used. For rivers, which hold delayed water in a queue and in the damping box, the processes are performed only in the damping box. Figure 3-2 illustrates nitrogen and phosphorus processes simulated by HYPE in rivers and lakes.

Figure 3-2. Nitrogen and phosphorus processes in rivers and lakes in HYPE (SMHI, 2023)

3.2. Data

E-HYPE uses open source datasets to create various inputs and settings of the model. The catchments are based off of MERIT HYDRO (Yamazaki et al., 2019) combined with the EU-Hydro (EU CLMS, 2019) dataset, with further subdivision driven by locations of stations with data available for calibration of streamflows and water quality concentrations. Land use, soil, agriculture, and Köppen-Geiger climate zones (Kottek et al., 2006) data were combined to define SLCs that serve as basic computational units in HYPE. As E-HYPE simulates pan-European domain, often two different sets of datasets were used for areas within and outside the European Union. Details are listed in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1. Data sources and methods used in E-HYPE4 model.

Data layer	Data source	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Reference
Catchments and flow network	MERIT HYDRO	Constant	Grid, 3 arc-second	Yamazaki et al., 2019
Lakes	EU-Hydro	Constant	Vector derived from 20m resolution	EU CLMS 2019
Land cover	CORINE CLC	2006	100m grid	CLC, 2021
	ESA CCI-LC	2010	300m grid	ESA, 2017
Soil types	ESDB	Constant	1km grid	Panagos, P., 2006
	DMSW	Constant	10km grid	FAO, 2003
Agriculture data	CAPRI	2010	NUTS2 administrative regions	CAPRI, 2024
	FAOSTAT	1990-2018	Country (BY, CH, MD, RU, UA)	FAOSTAT, 2018
	MIRCA2000	2000	5 arc minutes	Portmann et al, 2010
Nitrogen Atmospheric deposition	MATCH	2010	grid	EMEP, 2023
Domestic emissions (scattered dwelling and point sources)	HYDE Population	2010	grid	ESTAT, 2023
	Statistics on wastewater treatment	2010	Country	EEA
	UWWTD database	2012	Point coordinates	EEA, 2023a,b
Industrial emissions to water	EEA E-PRTR v 3.3	2010	Point coordinates	EEA 2012
Daily precipitation and air temperature	Hydro-GFD	1979 - 2020	0.25 degree	Berg et al, 2021

Data layer	Data source	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Reference
Monitoring data (streamflow)	Various; a compilation of regional to global open source datasets (e.g. GRDC, IMGW, SMHI, EWA, BHDC, ...)	1970-2020	Point coordinates	various
Monitoring data (water quality)	Various; a compilation of regional to global open source datasets (e.g., GEMSTATS, GLORICH, SLU, ...)	2000-2020	Point coordinates	various

3.3. Calibration strategy

E-HYPE4 is calibrated using an ensemble calibration approach described by Brendel et al., 2023. A sensible range of parameters is sampled using the Latin Hypercube approach. The final selected parameter sets and model routines optimized the model performance for discharge, long-term average evapotranspiration, and sediment and nutrient concentrations. The model parameters are defined for the whole domain without regionalization, with the exception of precipitation correction due to capture failure in e.g. mountain regions.

This preliminary calibration was executed as a method test, using the E-HYPE version from Brendel et al. (2019) as a starting point. The main objective of this preliminary calibration was to add nutrient simulation capability to E-HYPE4. At this stage, no updates were carried out for nutrient sources. The sources from a previous version (E-HYPE 3.1.9) were mapped to E-HYPE4 catchment delineations. Then, a limited calibration was performed to improve the baseline model performance. Model performance was assessed during calibration using the Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) model fit statistic (Gupta et al., 2009), Relative Error (RE, simulated minus observed divided by observed) and Scaled Relative Error (REs, simulated minus observed divided by simulated + observed).

For the discharge calibration, the ensemble of 20,000 candidate parameter sets was generated from 28 calibration parameters controlling discharge, soil erosion, and lake/reservoir siltation. Of the 28 parameters, 11 were general parameters, 13 were tied to soil type, and 4 were tied to land use class. Values were generated for each of the 8 soil types and 21 land use categories; thus, the total number of optimized parameters was 199 (11 general parameters + 13 soil parameters x 8 soil types + 4 land use parameters x 21 land use classes). The search range for each parameter was pre-defined subjectively based on prior experience, and relationships were specified between the coarse, medium, and fine texture soil types for various soil parameters to ensure that, for example, coarser texture soils had higher maximum percolation capacities than finer texture soils.

The discharge calibration was performed for the period of 1991-2010 using 193 stations for calibration and 1,465 independent stations for validation. A map of all discharge calibration and validation stations is provided in Figure 3-3. A spin-up period of 1981-1991 was included during the simulations to allow the model states to stabilize. The simulation period for the sediment calibration was 2001-2010 with a spin-up period of 1981-2001 to allow the model states to stabilize. The sediment calibration was performed using 131 stations for calibration and 802 independent stations for validation.

The goal of nutrient calibration was to perform a quick recalibration of the E-HYPE4 model for nutrients to reduce biases in the nutrient fluxes at the coastal areas. A total of 27 parameters were selected for calibration with 10,000 parameter sets to run. From these, the EHYPER-4 full domain model was run for a subset of 288 top-performing parameter sets. The objective was to maximize the KGE and minimize the absolute value of the median relative error for each substance (sediments, TN, TP, IN, ON, SP, and PP). Performance for discharge and ET were considered equally good for all parameter sets and were therefore excluded from the further recalibration.

Figure 3-3. Locations of calibration vs. validation stations for discharge. Note: RGB = Representative Gage Basin, i.e. calibration station.

3.4. Results and limitations

Model performance was evaluated in terms of KGE, NSE, and RE (Table 3-2, Figure 3-4). Streamflow is simulated with a median RE of -3.3%. Evapotranspiration and Total Phosphorus are simulated with a median RE less than 10% while sediment and total nitrogen have a median RE less than 20%. There is a large variability in model performances at individual sites, as it is expected from a large-scale model without regionalized parameters. However, there is a very little bias for the evaluated constituents with the exception for inorganic nitrogen that appears to be consistently underestimated. Organic nitrogen is mostly overestimated, balancing this underestimation.

Table 3-2. Model performance overview

Variable	NSE	Median		% sites within RE of			Number of stations
		RE	KGE	10%	25%	50%	
Streamflow	0.25	-3.3	0.48	33%	68%	89%	1015
Evapotranspiration	N/A	-8.2	N/A	39%	78%	95%	2671
Sediment	-0.35	19.1	-0.33	6%	16%	35%	933
Total Nitrogen	-3.62	-18.6	-0.15	11%	29%	59%	380
Total Phosphorus	-1.95	-5.7	-0.34	9%	22%	47%	657
Inorganic Nitrogen	-6.42	-53.6	-0.34	5%	16%	33%	553
Organic Nitrogen	-1.73	30.2	-0.28	13%	28%	54%	242
Soluble Phosphorus	-2.57	-2.1	-0.31	9%	27%	49%	508
Particulate Phosphorus	-1.78	-23.8	-0.38	4%	12%	30%	390

Note: * long term average was compared, thus statistics evaluating dynamics are not available (N/A)

The number of available stations and spatial representation vary for each simulated constituent, from 933 for sediment to 242 for organic nitrogen (Figure 3-5 to Figure 3-8). The preliminary calibration presented here shows a little bias in streamflow simulations and a high range in model performance for nutrients at the same time. The ongoing recalibration in WP4 in FOCCUS is needed to improve the simulation of nutrients with E-HYPE4 and to reduce the model performance spread.

Figure 3-4. Model performance for all monitoring stations evaluated as KGE and Scaled RE. Note: Q= streamflow, ET = evapotranspiration, TS = sediment (total suspended solids), TN = total nitrogen, TP = total phosphorus, IN = inorganic nitrogen, ON = organic nitrogen, SP = soluble (reactive) phosphorus, PP = particulate phosphorus

Figure 3-5. Relative error estimating streamflow

Figure 3-6. Relative error estimating TSS

Figure 3-7. Relative Error estimating TP

Figure 3-8. Relative error estimating TN.

4. JRC Freshwater Model

This section describes two models developed at the JRC for European freshwater: the LISFLOOD model for simulating stream flow (Section 4.1) and the GREEN model for simulating nutrient loads (Section 4.2).

4.1. LISFLOOD

4.1.1. Model structure

LISFLOOD is a spatially distributed, process based model that has been applied for flood prevention, river regulation, drought and soil moisture assessment, and for evaluating the impacts of climate and land-use changes on water resources.

A description of the overall structure of LISFLOOD can be found in the LISFLOOD user manual: https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/2_01_stdLISFLOOD_overview/. Figure 4.1 shows the model overall structure and its main hydrological processes. The manual also includes a detailed description of:

- 1) the soil classes, land use classes, crop classes used in LISFLOOD;
- 2) all model routines (<https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/>), such as for example
 - a) interception (https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/2_02_stdLISFLOOD_interception/);
 - b) soil moisture distribution (https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/2_12_stdLISFLOOD_soilmoisture-redistributi on/); and
 - c) channel routing (https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/2_16_stdLISFLOOD_channel-routing/).

Figure 4.1. Overview of processes considered in LISFLOOD. Adapted from Model Documentation overview, <https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/>

The model is under continuous improvement. Versioning of the source code is available here: <https://github.com/ec-jrc/lisflood-code/releases>. For discharge comparison and use in operative systems, it is recommended to use the latest river discharges directly available in the Copernicus data repository (<https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/efas-historical?tab=download>).

LISFLOOD is currently used within the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) and the Global Flood Awareness System (GLOFAS). Both EFAS and GLOFAS are operated under the Copernicus Emergency Management System (EMS). (https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/1_1_introduction_LISFLOOD/). The Open-Source (OS) LISFLOOD version used for the latest (EFAS version5.0) calibration is version 4.1.3. The latest available (OS) LISFLOOD is version 4.3.1 (status June 2024).

Please note that the mean annual discharge used in the GREEN model to derive mean annual nutrient concentrations comes from a different version of LISFLOOD that was developed to enable policy scenario analysis see De Roo et al. 2021; 2023).

A new EFAS version of LISFLOOD is expected to be released in Summer 2025. Within the project FOCCUS a better alignment between LISFLOOD discharge and GREEN nutrient modelling is foreseen.

4.1.2. Data

An overview of the sources of data used for the most recent calibration of OS LISFLOOD (EFAS version 5.0) is described in [Choulga et al. \(2023\)](#). The OS LISFLOOD used a large variety of geophysical data to describe the soil properties, land use, etc. These static maps are described in the user guide ([chapter “static maps”](#)). Finally, all maps are available in the JRC Data Catalogue (<https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/f572c443-7466-4adf-87aa-c0847a169f23>)

Meteorological forcing data was generated by interpolating meteorological observations. A description of this dataset (EMO - European Meteorological Observations) can be found in [Thiemig et al. \(2022\)](#). Please note that the latest calibration of OS LISFLOOD uses the EMO-1 dataset. EMO-1 provides grids with a spatial resolution of 1arcmin (approx. 1.5km) and covers the time period from 1990 until recent.

The full meteorological dataset is available at the JRC Data Catalogue (<https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset/0bd84be4-cec8-4180-97a6-8b3adaac4d26>). Make sure you have a look at the [README](#) document and [CHANGELOG](#) before using the dataset.

4.1.3. Calibration strategy

OS LISFLOOD is calibrated using observed river discharges. A complete overview of the river discharges used in the latest OS LISFLOOD calibration (EFAS version 5.0) can be found here: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CEMS/EFAS+v5.0+--+Calibration+Data>. Briefly, model calibration was conducted on 1903 calibration points, i.e. river gauging stations with drainage area larger than 150 km², that had at least 4 years of data (6-hourly discharge observations) from 1991 to 2021 and could be consistently identified in the model grid drainage network. The drained area of these stations covered 43.4% of the EFAS v5 pan-European domain.

Calibration of 14 model parameters was conducted for each station with the Distributed Evolutionary Algorithm for Python (DEAP, Fortin et al. 2012) to identify the parameter set that scored the highest value of the modified Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE', Gupta et al., 2009). When multiple calibration points were available in one basin, calibration proceeded head-catchments to downstream catchments. If a station had more than eight years of data a split calibration-validation process was implemented, using the most recent period for calibration, as more recent input data were considered more reliable. A spin-up period of three years was added to each model run to ensure that model's variable were correctly initialised.

A parameter regionalisation approach was adopted to transfer parameters that control snow melt, infiltration, runoff, groundwater, and routing to uncalibrated catchments. Calibrated

parameter values were transferred from calibrated catchments (donors) to uncalibrated catchments (receivers). Donor catchments were identified based on climatic and geographic proximity. Conversely, lake and reservoir parameters, which cannot be transferred based on these criteria, were set at default value. Finally, all coastal and endorheic catchments with drainage area smaller than 150 km² were modelled using the default parameter values. More details on the calibration strategy are described here: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CEMS/EFAS+v5.0+-+Calibration+Methodology+and+Data>.

4.1.4. Results and limitations

The performance of the latest OS LISFLOOD calibration is described here: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CEMS/EFAS+v5.0+-+Hydrological+Model+Performance>. The hydrological performance of LISFLOOD was measured with the modified Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE') (Knoben et al. 2019). The median KGE' in the 1903 station was 0.694. Spatially, KGE' scores were generally uniformly distributed across the model domain, with higher performance in large parts of central Europe. The lowest performances were generally noted in catchments with strongly regulated rivers.

LISFLOOD river discharge output from 1991 until recent for the latest calibration and as described above is available at CEMS Early Warning Datastore: <https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/efas-historical?tab=download>

4.2. GREEN

4.2.1. Model structure

The model distinguishes between two types of nutrient sources that undergo different pathways of retention along the river basin. Diffuse sources, including mineral fertilisers, manure, crop and soil fixation (only for nitrogen), atmospheric deposition and scattered dwellings emissions, are reduced by land and river (and lake) retention, while point sources, including industrial emissions and discharges from wastewater treatment plants, are reduced only by river (and lake) retention (Figure 4.2).

Land retention is simulated as an inverse function of annual precipitation, whereas river retention is modelled as a function of reach length. Lake retention is represented as a function of lake depth and hydraulic residence time. Retention in land and rivers is regulated by two parameters that are calibrated against observations of nutrient loads at monitoring stations. The GREEN model produces nutrient loads. The mean nutrient concentrations in rivers are then calculated by dividing these nutrient loads by the mean annual river discharge from the LISFLOOD model.

Figure 4.2. Schema of nutrient input and pathways represented in the GREEN model. (Basin retention is also called land retention in the text and GREEN model documentation).

The GREEN model is applied at a catchment resolution. The river network, catchments delineation and hierarchical relationships between catchment and stream segments are based on Catchment Characterisation Model (CCM2) that covers the entire European continent (de Jager and Vogt 2007). GREEN uses catchments of approximately 7 km² area. The total land extent considered covers 6.3M km², encompassing all river basins draining into European seas and spanning 44 countries (Figure 4.3).

The model equations are fully described in Grizzetti et al. (2021) and Vigiak et al. (2023). The GREEN model has been published as an open source model (Udias et al. 2023). The supporting R package, GREENeR, can be found at: <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/GREENeR/index.html>

The nitrogen and phosphorus load simulations for the period 1990-2021 provided for the FOCCUS project (D4.1) represent new results (from the GREEN model simulation version March 2024) and have not been yet published. For the equations, please refer to Vigiak et al. (2023); for open-source model code refer to Udias et al. (2023).

The LISFLOOD model version used here to derive nutrient concentrations from loads is described in De Roo et al. (2021, 2023), and includes coupling LISFLOOD with the crop model EPIC. Discharges thus slightly differ from, but are consistent with, LISFLOOD version described in the previous section. As part of FOCCUS modelling improvement, a better alignment of the discharge versions is planned.

Figure 4.3. Extent covered by the GREEN model simulation (version March 2024). Colours show the river basins draining into European marine regions and sub-regions as defined by the EU MSFD.

4.2.2. Data

The GREEN model integrates data on hydrology, land use, climate and anthropogenic pressures, notably nitrogen and phosphorus input from different sources (Table 4.1). All model input and output data are organized in a geo-database; data source and spatial and temporal resolution are described in Table 4.1. Catchments and stream network delineation and upstream-downstream hierarchy are derived from CCM2 (de Jager and Vogt, 2007). Lakes geometry is taken from Ecrins (EEA, 2012) and lake characteristics integrated from HydroLakes V1.0 (Messenger 2016). In each catchment, the area of main land cover classes (agricultural land, natural land, urban area and water) is based on CLC (2021) and ESA (2017). Mean annual precipitation is computed from EMO-5 and EMO-1 (Thiemig et al., 2022; Goncalo et al. 2020). Mean annual flows and irrigation volumes are obtained from the model LISFOOD coupled with the crop model EPIC (De Roo et al. 2021, 2023). Water flow values are assigned to each catchment outlet by spatial interpolation, as the river network of the GREENmodel and that of the LISFOOD model do not coincide.

Several nitrogen and phosphorus sources are represented in the GREEN model. Nutrients from mineral and manure fertilizers, and crop fixation for nitrogen, were taken from CAPRI model data (CAPRI, 2024), originally available at NUTS2 administrative regions, and allocated to each catchment proportionally to its agricultural land (CLC, 2021; ESA, 2017). For Belarus,

Moldova, Russia, Switzerland and Ukraine data from FAOSTAT (FAOSTAT, 2018) were adopted, as these countries are not covered by the CAPRI model. The annual time series of nitrogen atmospheric deposition was derived from the EMEP model (EMEP, 2023), while values of phosphorus atmospheric deposition were based on the global map of Mahowald et al. (2008). Domestic emissions of nutrients, including discharges from waste water treatment plants and emissions from scattered dwellings, were estimated using the methodology described in Vigiak et al. (2020), but including most recent data of UWWTD database (EEA, 2023a,b). Industrial emissions to water were derived from the Industrial Reporting under the Industrial Emissions Directive 2010/75/EU and European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 Ver 9.0 database (EEA, 2023c) as in Vigiak et al. (2023). Finally, observations for the model calibration from monitoring stations across all Europe were taken from the WISE SOE Waterbase (EEA, 2023d).

Table 4.1. Data sources and methods used in the GREEN model inputs for the historical simulation 1990-2021 (version March 2024).

Data layer	Data source	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Reference
Catchments and stream network	CCM2	Constant	Catchments (average 7 km ²)	de Jager and Vogt, 2007
Lakes	Ecrins	Constant	Lakes	EEA, 2012
	HydroLAKES v1.0	Constant	Lakes	Messenger et al., 2016
Land cover	CORINE CLC	2000, 2006, 2012, 2018	100m grid	CLC, 2021
	ESA CCI-LC	1992-2018	300m grid	ESA, 2017
Mineral, manure fertilization, plant biofixation	CAPRI	1990-2018	NUTS2 administrative regions (EU-27 countries, AL, BA, GB, ME, MK, NO, RS, TR, XK)	CAPRI, 2024 (baseline simulation version March 2024)
	FAOSTAT	1990-2018	Country (BY, CH, MD, RU, UA)	FAOSTAT, 2018
Nitrogen Atmospheric deposition	EMEP	1990-2021	0.1 degree grid	EMEP, 2023

Data layer	Data source	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Reference
Phosphorus Atmospheric deposition		Constant	2 degree grid	Mahowald et al., 2008
Domestic emissions (scattered dwelling and point sources)	ESTAT Population shares per treatment type	1990-2023	Country	ESTAT, 2023
	GHS-POP Population density	1990, 2000, 2015, 2020	1 km ² grid	Schiavina et al., 2023
	FAO nutrient content in diet	1990-2020	Country	Malagò and Bouraoui, 2021; FAOSTAT, 2023
	P content in detergents	1990-2018	Country	
	UWWTD database	2016, 2018, 2020	Point coordinates	EEA, 2023a,b
Industrial emissions to water	Reporting under the IED 2010/75/EU and EPRTR Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 v 9.0	2001, 2004, 2007-2021	Point coordinates	Vigiak et al., 2023; EEA, 2023c
Annual precipitation	EMO-5	1990-2019	5x5 km ² pixels	Thiemig et al., 2022
	EMO-1	2020-2021	Resampled to 5 km ² grid	Goncalo et al., 2020
Mean annual flow and irrigation volume	LISFLOOD-EPIC	1990-2021	5x5 km ² grid	De Roo et al., 2023; De Roo et al., 2021
Monitoring data (total nitrogen and total phosphorus)	WISE SOE Waterbase (EEA)	1990-2021	Point coordinates	EEA, 2023d

4.2.3. Calibration strategy

The GREEN model was calibrated for total nitrogen and total phosphorus in seven European regions, to take into account regional variability. The regions correspond to river basins and coastal catchments draining into the marine regions (or sub-regions) defined by the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (Table 4.2, Figure 4.2). Marine sub-regions with few reference values and located in proximity were grouped together.

Model parameters were calibrated using total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) data from the European WISE SOE Waterbase database (EEA, 2023d), which provides the average annual concentration, but does not include information on water discharges. To calculate annual loads needed to calibrate the model, the average annual observed concentration was multiplied by the mean annual discharge simulated by the LISFLOOD model for the same CCM2 catchment. Only the most downstream station was retained if multiple stations were located in the same catchment, and stations on secondary channels or far from the main reach of the catchment were excluded. The calibration was carried out over the period 2000-2020. A total of 34,509 data entries for TN and 52,458 for TP were utilized for the calibration (Table 4.3, Figure 4.4).

Table 4.2. Regions used for GREEN model calibration. For the extent of the marine regions and sub-regions see Figure 4.3.

Region	Marine region or sub-region	Land extent (km²)	CCM2 stream network length (km)
ABI	Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast	660,444	230,827
ACS	Celtic Seas	196,484	55,944
ANS	Greater North Sea, incl. the Kattegat and the English Channel	954,476	287,424
BAL	Baltic Sea	1,653,172	473,695
BLK	Black Sea, and Sea of Marmara	1,121,650	388,489
BNW	Barents Sea, Norwegian Sea, White Sea	438,661	134,575
MED	Adriatic Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea, Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea, and Western Mediterranean Sea	1,110,094	495,131

Four criteria were computed for evaluating the goodness of fit of the calibration, as they inform on different aspects, including:

- NSE (Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency): residual variance compared to the measured data variance.
- KGE (Kling-Gupta Efficiency): looks at the variance (like NSE), but also the bias (mean) and the correlation of the observed vs. modelled.
- rNSE (relative Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency): modification of the NSE. It adjusts the NSE by the range of observed data, making it less sensitive to extreme values.
- mNSE (modified Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency): variant of the NSE that is less sensitive to high values.

While all criteria were checked, the final choice of the best parameter set for each region of calibration was based on the NSE, which gives more weight to the performance in the simulation of nutrient load at river basin outlets.

Table 4.3. Number of observations used in the calibration of the GREEN model for total nitrogen (a) and total phosphorus (b) per region of calibration. The regions of calibration are described in Table 4.2.

	Number of observations per region of calibration							Number of observations per region of calibration						
	total nitrogen							total phosphorus						
	ABI	ACS	ANS	BAL	BLK	BNW	MED	ABI	ACS	ANS	BAL	BLK	BNW	MED
2000	81	11	245	545	76	21	52	170	20	413	555	284	16	139
2001	76	11	242	545	81	21	58	164	17	415	560	285	16	234
2002	51	10	249	565	78	21	112	204	19	420	560	289	16	325
2003	138	13	370	564	127	21	304	229	17	425	563	384	16	444
2004	145	15	401	559	142	33	331	271	21	481	558	522	32	487
2005	180	17	403	562	145	37	371	336	36	495	559	525	37	487
2006	306	57	586	497	159	32	257	576	81	693	497	482	32	339
2007	553	129	727	468	178	32	1444	819	146	767	494	300	32	1996
2008	779	123	846	455	218	33	1176	1207	135	905	481	333	33	1735
2009	831	137	794	426	197	32	585	1096	144	954	478	359	32	899
2010	385	177	474	381	227	31	1001	1454	221	1004	396	365	31	1780
2011	14	170	552	605	284	32	913	896	212	1106	618	373	32	1713
2012	63	163	525	983	269	26	920	936	210	1071	999	365	26	1734
2013	389		76	123	107		198			310	161	173		
2014	442		77	114	113		164			314	148	174		
2015	410		77	13	112		146			320	47	175		5
2016	373		74	13	111		49	582		305	43	175		293

2017	194		75	13	110		26	566		312	49	176		339
2018	303		76	13	111		46			737	152	360		5
2019	611		230	32	113		195			694	143	334		5
2020	494		76	13	111		205	530		525	124	293		256
Total	6818	1033	7175	7489	3069	372	8553	10036	1279	12666	8185	6726	351	13215

a)

b)

Figure 4.4. Location of calibration stations of the GREEN model for total nitrogen (a) and total phosphorus (b) and number of observations per station.

4.2.4. Results and limitations

Annual nutrient loads and concentrations were computed for the period 1990-2021. The performance of the GREEN model calibration was good in all regions apart from the BNW region, where fewer observations were available for calibration (Table 4.3). In the other regions, the NSE was between 0.79 and 0.96 for TN model and between 0.63 and 0.86 for TP model (Table 4.4). Annual plots of simulated versus observed nutrient load show a good model performance in both TN and TP over the period of calibration (Figure 4.5, Figure 4.6).

The GREEN model produces simulations of TN and TP load at each catchment outlet, as well as estimation of TN and TP concentration based on the annual water discharge provided by the model LISFLOOD. In addition, the model provides an estimation of the contribution of different sources to the total load (Figure 4.7).

Table 4.4. Results of the goodness of fit of the calibration of the GREEN model for total nitrogen and total phosphorus per region of calibration. The regions of calibration are described in Table 4.2. NSE: Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency; KGE: Kling-Gupta Efficiency; rNSE: relative Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency; mNSE: modified Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency.

	Total nitrogen				Total phosphorus			
Region	NSE	KGE	rNSE	mNSE	NSE	KGE	rNSE	mNSE

ABI	0.851	0.873	-199.7	0.73	0.667	0.679	72.313	0.617
ACS	0.787	0.862	0.9336	0.652	0.744	0.764	0.3894	0.5677
ANS	0.960	0.975	-171.4	0.8441	0.771	0.873	0.3283	0.6995
BAL	0.856	0.921	-2.239	0.7395	0.860	0.929	0.8594	0.713
BLK	0.933	0.956	0.7705	0.8572	0.801	0.881	0.676	0.7755
BNW	0.335	0.571	0.8488	0.4416	0.201	0.505	-2.708	0.2748
MED	0.957	0.935	0.8214	0.8588	0.634	0.728	84.30	0.6009

a) BAL region

b) MED region

Figure 4.5. Simulated versus observed total nitrogen load for available years from 2000 to 2020 in the BAL (a) and MED (b) regions.

a) ANS region

b) ABI region

Figure 4.6. Simulated versus observed total phosphorus load for available years from 2000 to 2020 in the ANS (a) and ABI (b) regions.

a) Baltic Sea region - Nitrogen load

b) Baltic Sea region - Phosphorus load

Figure 4.7. Total nitrogen load (a) and total phosphorus load (b) discharged to the Baltic Sea marine region (BAL) simulated by the GREEN model for the period 2000-2021 (version March 2024). Colors indicate the contribution of different sources: mineral fertilizer (Min), manure (Man), nitrogen biofixation (Fix), soil fixation (Soil), atmospheric deposition (Atm), scattered dwellings (Sd) and point sources (Ps).

5. Summary

This deliverable presents two existing continental modelling systems simulating discharge and nutrients in European streams. The SMHI's E-HYPE is one integrated model simulating nutrients and their flow from source to sea at the same time. The JRC's system uses two linked models: LISFLOOD simulating discharge and GREEN simulating nutrients.

Future work within the FOCCUS project will further improve the models and explore model differences and performances. In any case, both systems provide riverine inputs to coastal systems. Both systems provide daily discharge, but E-HYPE4 provides nutrients loads and concentrations as well as sediments daily while the JRC's system annually. This and other differences that are critical for coastal model users are highlighted in Table 5.1. Differences related to the model input data, model routines, and spatial structure are discussed in the sections below.

Table 5.1. Riverine outputs provided by European freshwater model systems.

	E-HYPE	JRC LISFLOOD/GREEN
Spatial resolution	All outputs: basins of mean area 170 km ²	Discharge: grid 1 arcmin resolution Water quality: subcatchments of mean 7 km ² area
Temporal resolution	Daily	Discharge: daily Water quality: annual
Available period*	2000-2019	1990-2021
Outputs	Discharge, total suspended solids, total nitrogen, total phosphorus, inorganic nitrogen, organic nitrogen, soluble (reactive) phosphorus, particulate phosphorus	Discharge, total nitrogen, total phosphorus
* - the periods will be harmonized in the final delivery		

Data

The two model systems use European-wide open databases that provide the basic information of land use/land cover and nutrient sources, particularly diffuse agricultural and atmospheric deposition, as well as domestic and industrial point source inputs (Tables 3.1 and 4.1). The sources of geophysical data are significantly overlapping for both models, e.g. in land use, lake extent, etc. There are only minor differences in elevation, soils, and crop data. An important difference is in the weather forcing data - E-HYPE utilises reanalysis (which may underestimate extreme precipitation), LISFLOOD use interpolation of observation data (which may introduce errors in certain areas, e.g. in the mountains). The main differences in the model input data are summarized from respective sections of this document in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. Differences in the input data between E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN.

	E-HYPE	JRC LISFLOOD/GREEN
Weather (atm.forcing)	Reanalysis Hydro-GFD, 0.25 degree (Berg et al, 2021)	Observation data EMO-5, 5x5 km ² pixels (Thiemig et al., 2022), EMO-1 5 km ² grid (Goncalo et al., 2020)
Catchments and stream network	MERIT HYDRO Grid, 3 arc-second (Yamazaki et al., 2019)	CCM2 Catchments (average 7 km ²) (de Jager and Vogt, 2007)
Lakes	EU-Hydro	Ecrins, HydroLAKES v1.0
Soil types	ESDB, DMSW (Panagos, P., 2006, FAO 2003)	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC) SoilGrids250m global gridded soil information, release 2017
Phosphorus Atmospheric deposition	not used	Mahowald et al., 2008
Nitrogen Atmospheric deposition	Engardt, et.al., 2013	EMEP MSC-W modelled air concentrations and depositions (https://www.emep.int/mscw/index.html) (EMEP, 2023)
Domestic emissions (scattered dwelling and point sources)	HYDE Population, Statistics on wastewater treatment, GHS-POP, UWWTD	ESTAT Population shares per treatment type, GHS-POP, FAO nutrient content in diet, UWWTD
Mean annual flow and irrigation volume	GMIA, MIRCA	LISFLOOD-EPIC 5x5 km ² grid (De Roo et al., 2023)

Monitoring data (water quality)	Various; a compilation of regional to global open source datasets (e.g., GEMSTATS, GLORICH, SLU, ...)	WISE SOE Waterbase (EEA)
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Main routines

Both models simulate daily discharge using process-based approach and robust spatial calibration/validation procedures. Figures 3.1 and 4.1 indicate a general common structure in the main identification of hydrological processes. However, calibration data and strategies may lead to rather different daily discharge simulations.

The main routines are highlighted in table 5.3. All the entries in this table are significantly simplified. For the details see the relative sections in this entire document.

Table 5.3. Differences in the main routines between E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN.

	E-HYPE	JRC LISFLOOD/GREEN
Rainfall-runoff process	daily/subdaily water balance, subbasin scale	daily/subdaily water balance, gridded
Potential evapotranspiration method	modified Jensen-Haise/McGuinness (Oudin et.a., 2005)	Penman-Monteith
Snow processes, melting	Threshold temperature for rain/snow separation, Degree-day for snow melt	Threshold temperature for rain/snow separation, Degree-day for snow melt
Channel routing	Simplified routing schemes: concentration time, river velocity, damping	Kinematic wave equations
Nutrient sources	Atmospheric deposition, fertilizer application, point sources, septs and other diffuse sources. Plant residues are added to the soils.	Atmospheric deposition, fertilizer application, point sources, disconnected domestic emissions, nitrogen fixation by plants and soils
Soil processes	Nutrients are coupled with the water flows through the soil layers, both as immobile soil pools and as different nutrient fractions dissolved (or suspended) in soil water. Transformation processes are included, e.g. crop uptake, erosion, denitrification, and mobilisation between the soil pools	Land retention of diffuse sources comprises plant uptake in crops in agricultural land, and is an exponential decay that depends on annual precipitation, regulated through a calibration parameter.

River processes	Nutrients simulated as IN, ON, SP, and PP. Transport and transformation processes such as sedimentation and resuspension, mineralisation, primary production, denitrification. Internal load constant for each water body, triggered by temperature threshold.	River retention is an exponential decay based on river length, used as a proxy of residence time, regulated through a calibration parameter. Lake retention is a function of lake hydraulic residence time.
Changing land use	Constant land use for the simulation time period	Area fraction of major land use classes (agriculture, water, forest, urban) changes in time, set according to Corine land cover
Calibration	Daily Q, ET, TS, TN, TP calibrated simultaneously. Non-regionalized.	Daily and sub-daily Q, annual TN and TP. Regionalized.
Model evaluation criteria	Daily KGE, Relative error (RE%), NSE, Correlation, processes rate evaluation (sedimentation, snow accumulation etc.)	Daily Q: KGE, modified KGE (KGE') (Knoben et al. 2019). Annual TN, TP based on NSE
Model performance (simplified)	All daily variables NSE (RE%): Streamflow: 0,48 (-3.3%) TS: -0.33 (19.1%) TN: -0.15 (-18%) TP: -0.34 (-5.7%)	Streamflow daily: median KGE' 0.69 Annual TN: NSE 0.79-0.96 (depending on a region) Annual TP: NSE 0.63-0.86 (depending on a region)

Spatial structure

The JRC's modeling system uses higher spatial resolution while E-HYPE provides higher temporal resolution for all its outputs.

Figure 5.1 shows an example of JRC modelling spatial resolution depicting North of Italy and Po River Basin, where LISFLOOD raster grid is overlaid with GREEN basins. The differences in the spatial and temporal resolution of JRC modelling system outputs may represent a difficulty in retrieving model outputs at the sea outlets.

Figure 5.1. The example of JRC model spatial resolution, depicting North of Italy and Po River Basin. The background color indicates LISFLOOD drainage area accumulation to highlight the main river pixels (in lighter color). Orange lines delineate GREEN basins. The white area is the Mediterranean sea.

Figure 5.2 shows an example of the SMHI E-HYPE model spatial resolution, depicting the same area - North of Italy and Po River Basin , coastal outlet points and subbasins delineation .

Figure 5.2. The example of the SMHI E-HYPE model spatial structure - Po River Basin (filled area), coastal outlets (orange dots) and subbasins delineation (purple borders)

Coastal users are encouraged to explore outputs from both models to assess their performance in the area of interest. The availability of two different systems allows as well ensemble modelling of riverine outputs and an assessment of uncertainties is riverine inputs to downstream systems.

Calibration approach

E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN models have different calibration approaches. E-HYPE is calibrated simultaneously for all the variables without regionalization. LISFLOOD is calibrated to simulate streamflow in gauged catchments, then parameters are transferred to geographically adjacent ungauged catchments via regionalization. The GREEN model is calibrated to simulate annual nutrients with use of regional approach in parameter estimation.

Regionalization usually helps to increase local model performance, but may increase uncertainty under some conditions as well as for e.g. climate change scenarios and may result in overparameterization of the model. The detailed comparison of the models is planned within WP5.

Reference to **MS4.1** - Improvement plan

Improvement plan stipulated within the FOCCUS project is described in milestone **MS4.1** (see Annex). Here we indicate major directions of the planned development while the improvement plans are being formulated.

The E-HYPE4 model for discharge, sediments, nitrogen, and phosphorus is being updated constantly based on what we learned from the previous model calibrations and analyses. During the period of WP4 and WP5 we update selected model inputs (point and rural source data, discharge data, and nutrient data) and improve the model performance. . Further improvements of runoff and nutrient and sediment loads at coastal outlets are planned using machine learning (ML) techniques to post-process E-HYPE outputs as a part of hybrid methodology following Pechlivanidis and Du, 2024. Hybrid methods combine process-based modelling and statistical or machine learning post-processors to improve streamflow predictive accuracy, including extremes.

Similarly, improvements in the model performance are planned for the JRC system. In particular, we will:

- reconcile GREEN spatial resolution with that of LISFLOOD,
- develop a procedure to redistribute annual nutrient loads to daily fluxes (loads and concentrations);
- and improve the internal consistency of input data between LISFLOOD and GREEN.

The release of a new calibration version (EFAS6) is planned in 2025, which will be included in the analysis. The EFAS6 version will also include improvements in soil input data, reservoirs and lakes spatial dataset and routines, and in irrigation fraction estimation.

Annex

Milestone MS4.1 summary:

Milestone MS4.1: New hydrological components and EBM improvements designed was delivered in October 2024, as part of WP4, and consisted of a work plan for new improvements. A summary of this document can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, as commented in the submission of this milestone in the EU Portal, the Commission has the right to request access to this document directly using the project's shared drive here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1DZEUvscZCNxDDtV24YnY6ll7Q15cEW33/view?usp=sharing>

This milestone presents ongoing improvements of two hydrological modelling systems (E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN) and comprehensive information about estuarine modelling system EBM (including SHYFEM-MPI), their structure, domains, data and validation. Proposed workflow for hydrological models under WP4/5 include improvements on nutrient representation, extension of used data and development of hybrid modelling systems based on ML (E-HYPE), focusing on the optimisation of constituents income at coastal outlets, and spatial adapting of the modelling systems structure to each other (LISFLOOD and GREEN). The estuarine modelling system is being tested on the representative objects, improved to represent the mixing processes and to provide the interaction between inland runoff and marine aquatories.

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